

A survey on the demand of the database of the Yellow River governance landscape in past dynasties in China

Hello everyone! We are writing a paper on the construction of the database of the Yellow River governance landscape in past dynasties in China , and it is important to get your suggestions on this database construction.

It takes about 5 minutes to complete the questionnaire. Sincerely thank you for taking your precious time to help our research!

1. How old are you? [fill in the blank] *

2. What is your education degree? [Single choice] *

Undergraduate

Master

Doctor

Other _____

3. What's your status? [Multiple choice] *

Student

Teacher

Expert and researcher

Other _____

4. What is your discipline and research direction/interest? [fill in the blank] *

Such as: Chinese History, Historiographical Theory and Historiography

5. What's the rank of the Yellow River in largest rivers in China? ¹ What's the rank of the Yellow River in largest rivers in the world? ² [please fill in the numbers in brackets]

*

First

second

third

fourth

Fifth

6. Where did the Yellow River originate? [single choice] *

Northern foothills of Bayan Har Mountain, Qinghai-Tibet Plateau

Southern foothills of Bayan Har Mountain, Qinghai-Tibet Plateau

7. What provinces does the Yellow River flow through? [Multiple Choices] *

Qinghai

Xinjiang

Gansu

Sichuan

Ningxia

Inner Mongolia

Shaanxi

Shanxi

Henan

Hebei

Shandong

8. The Yellow River traverses three steps, and which topographical and landform areas does the Yellow River pass through? [Multiple Choices] *

Qinghai-Tibet Plateau

Inner Mongolia Plateau

- Loess Plateau
- North China Plain
- Shanxi-Shaanxi Canyon
- Sichuan Basin
- Taihang Mountains

9. What are the important irrigation areas in the Yellow River Basin? [Multiple Choices]

*

- Ningxia Irrigation District
- Hetao Irrigation District
- Fenhe Valley
- Guanzhong Basin
- Huanghuaihai Plain
- Huangshui Valley
- Chengdu Plain

10. What are the characteristics of the river nature of the Yellow River? [Multiple Choices] *

- easily clogged
- easily burst
- easily changed

11. For over 2500 years, how many times has the Yellow River ruptured¹, how many times has the Yellow River diversified², and how many times has the Yellow River major diversified³? [Sort questions, please fill in the numbers in brackets] *

[] More than 1400 times

[] More than 1500 times

[] More than 1600 times

24 times

25 times

26 times

4 times

5 times

6 times

12. Before the diversion in the fifth year of Xianfeng in the Qing Dynasty (AD 1855), which provinces and regions did the lower Yellow River flow through and flow into which sea areas? ¹ After the diversion, which provinces and regions did the lower Yellow River flow through and flow into which sea area? ² [Sort questions, please fill in the numbers in brackets] *

Henan, Anhui, Shandong, Jiangsu, Yellow Sea

Henan, Zhili (now Hebei Province), Shandong, Bohai Sea

Henan, Anhui, Jiangsu, Yellow Sea

Henan, Shandong, Bohai

13. Which of the following belong to the Yellow River governance figures and their strategies? [Multiple Choice Questions] *

Great Yu and his strategy for dredging the river

Li Bing and Dujiangyan

Jia Rang and his three strategies for governing the river

Pan Jixun's "storing clean water and brushing the Yellow River" and "bounding water and attacking sand"

Kangxi and his three policies

Li Yizhi, and his comprehensive governance of upstream, middle and downstream of the Yellow River

14. What are the officials or institutions that governed the Yellow River in history?

[Multiple Choices] *

- Sikong
- Situ
- Sichuan
- Dushuiguan
- River embankment visitor
- Governor of the River
- Governor of Water Transport
- Zonghe
- Water Department
- Yellow River Water Commission

15. Which of the following documents is related to the governance of the Yellow River?

[Multiple Choices] *

- "Shangshu·Yugong"
- "Zhizheng River Defense"
- "List of River Defenses"
- "Xingshui Jinjian"
- "Shui Jing Zhu Annotation Map"
- "Illustration of River Tools"
- "List of natural and man-made disasters in past dynasties"
- Twenty-five Histories of the River Canal
- Ming and Qing records
- Ming and Qing local chronicles

16. Do you think that the comparative study of the river governance strategies in history is still helpful for the governance of the Yellow River today? [Single choice] *

- Yes

○No

Landscape is an objective presentation of the relationship between human and land, reflecting the complex interactions and changes between human activities and ecosystems.

The **Yellow River governance landscape in past dynasties** embodies the process of interaction and reaction between human and the Yellow River in historical periods. We divide the Yellow River governance landscape into the following four types:

1. The changing landscape of the Yellow River, mainly referring to the changes of the river source, river channel and river delta;
2. Engineering landscape, mainly referring to the river defense system and irrigation system;
3. Economic-social landscape, including shipping and water transportation, the formation and changes of cities and villages along the Yellow River, the economic zone of the Yellow River Basin, the political-military center, etc.;
4. Ideological and cultural landscape, including documents on the governance of the Yellow River, relics of the governance of the Yellow River, the spirit of governance of the Yellow River, folk beliefs and regional culture, etc..

17. If you are to build the database of the Yellow River governance landscape, what is the order of construction of the four parts of the Yellow River governance landscape? [Sort questions, please fill in the numbers in brackets] *

[] The changing landscape of the Yellow River

[] Engineering landscape

[] Economic-Social Landscape

[] Ideological and cultural landscape

18. If you have other suggestions for the construction of the database, please fill in the blank:

19. What types of historical information do you think the Yellow River governance landscape database needs to provide? [Multiple Choices] *

Original documents: many types of historical documents, archaeological excavation reports, scientific investigation reports, etc.

Non-original documents: books, chronology, etc.

Pictures: maps, maps, images, etc.

Video category: interviews, reports, etc.

Other _____

20. Do you need a database with detailed historical information on levee systems and irrigation systems? [Single choice] *

Not required 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 very necessary

21. Do you need a database to provide historical information such as the time and frequency of floods in the Yellow River, as well as corresponding governance measures? [Single choice] *

Not required 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 very necessary

22. Do you need a database to provide historical information such as manpower, material and financial resources for the governance of the Yellow River? [Single choice] *

Not required 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 very necessary

23. Do you need a database to provide historical images of the Yellow River landscape? For example: various types of Yellow River maps, river defense engineering pictures, architectural figures, topographic maps of the Yellow River Basin, and so on. [Single choice] *

Not required 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 very necessary

24. Do you need a visualization tool for the text provided by the database, such as the visualization of events related to the governance of Huanghuai Yun in the Qingkou area (now Huai'an City, Jiangsu Province) during the Ming and Qing Dynasties? [Single choice] *

Not required
 1
 2
 3
 4
 5
 6
 7
 8
 9
 very necessary

25. Do you need the database to provide visual analysis tools (linear map and social network analysis) of people, such as the figure of people who governed the Yellow River in past dynasties as shown in the figure below? [Single choice] *

○Not required ○1 ○2 ○3 ○4 ○5 ○6 ○7 ○8 ○9 ○ very necessary

26. Do you need the database to provide map-type visual analysis and tools (GIS, geographic information system), for example, to map and mark the historical changes of the main and tributaries of the Yellow River?

[Single choice] *

○Not required ○1 ○2 ○3 ○4 ○5 ○6 ○7 ○8 ○9 ○ very necessary

27. What aspects do you need to retrieve the resources in the Yellow River Governance Landscape Database? [Multiple Choices] *

- Time (A.D. chronology and Chinese traditional chronology)
- Geographical location (ancient and modern place names)
- Governance figures (name, job title, etc.)
- Type of disaster (diversion, flood, drought, etc.)
- River governance projects (dykes, gates, dams, etc.)
- Tools and materials for river management
- Keywords (such as entries and subject headings in "Hegong Ciyuan", "Xingshui Jinjian", "Xu Xingshui Jinjian Classification Index")
- Other _____

28. Which of the following databases have you used? [Multiple Choice Questions] *

- China Basic Ancient Books Library
- China Digital Local Chronicles Database
- Journal Database of China in Late Qing Dynasty and Republic of China
- Gale Scholar
- Chinese Biographical Database (CBDB)

- China's classic water conservancy historical literature database (China Water Press)
- Qing Dynasty Natural Disaster Information Database
- Other _____

29. Which of the following digital humanities related tools and methods have you heard of? [Multiple Choices] *

- Social network analysis
- Text Analysis
- Named Entity Recognition
- GIS, geographic information system
- Python
- Other _____

30. What kinds of services do you need in the use of the Yellow River Landscape Database provided by library? [Multiple Choices] *

- Consultation by telephone, email, etc.
- Special lecture on database usage
- Relevant software usage training (such as map software)
- Demonstration guidance by experts in relevant disciplines
- Other _____